

Kinetic Studies of the Oxidation of Tartaric Acid by Ammoniacal Silver Nitrate

A. P. Modi and S. Ghosh

The kinetic studies of the oxidation of tartrate by ammoniacal silver nitrate reveals that the order of the reaction with respect to silver in solution is one and that it is zero order with respect to tartrate in most of the cases. The increasing concentration of ammonia decreases the rate and is marked by an induction period. The values of temperature coefficient for 10° rise, energy and entropy of activation have been found to be 3.20, 22.0 K cal. and -5.69 e.u. respectively.

The product of oxidation has been identified mainly as oxalic acid, formed by the fission of the molecule of the tartaric acid at -HOHC-CHOH- . The mechanism of the oxidation is suggested through the formation of a coordinated compound with a molecule of tartaric acid and silver ions.

Reduction of argento-ammine by several organic compounds is well known and is a specific reaction for an aldehydic group. Dhar¹ has reported that no reduction of silver nitrate takes place even on prolonged boiling with such organic acids as malic, tartaric, citric but formate is oxidisable by silver nitrate. However, ammoniacal silver nitrate is used for qualitative detection of tartrate which yields metallic silver, but neither any kinetic study has been made of this reaction nor a mechanism has been suggested and products identified.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either A.R, E Merck or B.D.H. extra pure quality. The solutions were prepared by using doubly distilled water in Jena measuring flask. The standard solution of silver nitrate was prepared freshly and was always kept in dark to avoid any photochemical reaction. The organic substrate was standardised by titration with a standard alkali. The potassium sulphocyanide solution was standardised by Volhard's method.

A common difficulty in the study of the kinetics of this oxidation by ammoniacal silver nitrate is the partial loss of ammonia during the progress of the reaction. The experimental procedure adopted in this study considerably checked it by using smaller concentrations of ammonia and maintaining the vapour pressure of ammonia constant over the reaction mixture during the course of the experiment. This is achieved by performing the experiments in a closed vessel by contacting it by means of a bent tube with another conical flask containing the same concentration of ammoniacal silver nitrate solution. The aliquots were withdrawn at different intervals by means of a self-designed three-way stopcock pipette (volume discharged 6.2 mls.) attached to the reaction vessel, so as not to open the cork of the flask. Both the flasks were previously coated outside with black Japan to avoid

1. Dhar: *Proc. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1916, **24**, 947.

photochemical reaction, and were kept in thermostat maintained at a desired temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ range. The reaction mixture, thus pipetted out, was taken in a pyrex test tube containing 1-2 ml. saturated solution of barium nitrate and 10 mls. of 0.3 *M* ammonia to precipitate the colloidal silver and check the reaction completely because the solution becomes dilute and larger concentrations of ammonia directly retard the reaction rate (see table 3) so much so that in presence of 0.2 *M* ammonia, no appreciable reduction of silver took place within one hour of observation. This is quickly filtered through a sintered glass crucible into a flask containing few mls. of nitric acid. The excess of silver was estimated by Volhard's method.

In all the experiments, the total silver ion has been estimated which is proportional to free silver ion present in the reaction mixture. Thus, if 'x' is the amount of silver free out of the total silver ion 'C' present in the ammoniacal solution, then:

$$x = \frac{C}{K(\text{NH}_3)^n + 1} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where 'K' is stability constant of the ammine $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_n^+$. If the concentration of free ammonia is kept constant for a particular run, obviously, 'x' is proportional to 'C' or the concentration of total silver estimated at any time.

In most of the experiments, it is observed that there exists an induction period for reaction and that it becomes very significant when ammonia concentration in the reaction mixture has been high. For such cases, the rate constants have been calculated after the expiry of this induction period, and the results are reproducible. The data of one typical experiment have been recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

(Tartrate)=0.10*M*
(Silver Nitrate)=0.020*M*

(Ammonium Hydroxide)=0.0416*M*
Temperature=35°

Time	0.025 <i>M</i> KCNS in ml.	$K_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0	4.98	—
5	4.66	—
10	3.96	22.52
15	3.34	26.37
20	2.96	25.81
25	2.74	23.74
30	2.60	21.54
Average		23.99

This shows that the reaction follows first order law satisfactorily with respect to silver in solution.

Effect of Tartrate on Reaction Rate: In order to find the order with respect to the reductant, the kinetics has been studied in the presence of different concentrations of tartrate using the same amount of ammonia. The values of the rate constants are recorded in the Table II.

TABLE II

	(Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M (Ammonium Hydroxide) = 0.0416M Temperature = 30°		
Tartrate	0.15M	0.10M	0.050M
$K_1 \times 10 \text{ min}^{-1}$	14.14	13.88	14.37

The above table shows that there is no appreciable effect on the rate constants. Hence the order of the reaction for the oxidation of tartrate or tartaric acid by ammoniacal silver nitrate is one with respect to silver ion but zero order with respect to tartrate.

Effect of Ammonia: Different concentrations of ammonia were used to study the effect of ammonia on rate constants. The effect is marked by an induction period, and the first order constants considerably decrease with the increase of ammonia concentrations. The effect of ammonia on rate constants is notable in the following table:

TABLE III

	(Tartrate) = 0.10M Temperature = 35°		
Concentrations of ammonia	0.0416M	0.0520M	0.0832M
$K_1 \times 10 \text{ min}^{-1}$	23.99	9.365	5.045

It is clear from the above table that there is a sharp fall in rate constants so much so that by increasing the concentration of ammonia twice i.e., from 0.0416M to 0.0832M, the rate constant becomes about 1/5th.

Influence of Temperature and Temperature-Coefficient: The reaction velocities were measured at different temperatures (table IV). All the experiments were performed at identical conditions.

TABLE IV

	(Tartrate) = 0.1M (Silver Nitrate) = 0.02M (Ammonium Hydroxide) = 0.0520M		
Temperature	40°	35°	30°
$K_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	16.01	9.364	4.727

The rate of reaction between tartrate and ammoniacal silver nitrate increases with increase in the temperature. The average temperature coefficient for 10° rise in temperature is calculated in presence of 0.1M tartrate, 0.0520M and 0.0624M ammonia, and is found to be 3.20.

Energy and Entropy of Activation: The values of energy and entropy of activation are calculated, when 0.1M tartrate in presence of 0.0520M ammonia has been used and are found to be 22.0 K cal, and -5.69 e.u. respectively.

DISCUSSION

The complete oxidation of tartaric acid to carbon dioxide and water requires five atoms of oxygen and the determination of equivalents shows that only three oxygen atoms

are utilized by a mole of tartrate when oxidised by ammoniacal silver nitrate. The final product of oxidation is necessarily an organic compound which is not oxidisable by ammoniacal silver nitrate and is obtained by utilisation of three atoms of oxygen by a gm. mole of tartrate. The oxidation product of tartaric acid of different oxidising agents, as reported by different workers^{2,3,4}, is either aldehyde or formic acid. Ammoniacal silver nitrate oxidises an aldehyde, and silver salts also oxidise formic acid to carbon dioxide and water. It is, therefore, clear that these organic compounds can not be oxidised products of tartaric acid in the present case. However, unlike other oxidising agents, ammoniacal silver nitrate does not oxidise an oxalate or oxalic acid and therefore, we may conclude that in general oxalate is the final product formed by the oxidation of tartaric acid by ammoniacal silver nitrate and qualitative test for this organic compound in the solution left after the oxidation confirms this contention. In order to yield oxalic acid from tartaric acid, the following path is possible:

In an ammoniacal solution of silver nitrate, silver ion is present in free state as well as silver amines, $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)^+$ and $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_2^+$, depending upon the concentration of ammonia used. It will be seen from table III that the rate of reduction of silver decreases with increasing the concentration of ammonia. It is, therefore, clear that the reduction of silver ion is due to free Ag^+ ions in alkaline medium. It will be also seen from the relation (1) that the total silver estimated (used for calculating the rate constants) at various intervals of time is directly proportional to free Ag^+ ions in the conditions of the experiment described earlier.

In a very recent paper Mehrotra and Ghosh⁵ have concluded that the decomposition of tartaric acid by quadrivalent cerium occurs through the formation of a coordinated compound due to lone pairs of electrons of oxygen in $-\text{CHOH}$ group. Silver ion is also known to form complex salts and it is quite possible that similar coordination occurs in the present case as well, so that the fission of a tartaric acid molecule occurs at $-\text{HOHC}-\text{CHOH}-$.

The whole mechanism of the reduction of silver ions to metallic silver can now be represented as shown below:

2. Fleury and Lange, *Comp. rend.*, 1932, **195**, 1395-7, *ibid*, 1933, **195**, 313-26

3. Orlov, *J. Russian Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **43**, 1524-54.

4. Benarath and Ruland, *Z. Anorg. Allegem. Chem.*, 1920, **114**, 267-277.

Willard and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 132-42,

5. Mehrotra and Ghosh, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, (In press).

The formation of complexes represented as (2) and (3) are likely to be instantaneous and as the concentrations of tartrate are very high, the concentration of the complex formed is mostly proportional to silver ion concentrations and hence, if reaction (5) is the main rate determining step, the reduction of silver ions by tartrate will be of first order. If, however, the reaction (4) is fast but not instantaneous such that its speed is comparable to the speed of the reaction (5), the reduction of silver will have an induction period.

DEPARTMENT OF POST GRADUATE STUDIES
AND RESEARCH IN CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF JABALPUR,
JABALPUR.

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